

Blood

Biofluid and excreta

Biological location

Feces

Urine

Saliva

Cerebrospinal fluid

Cytoplasm
Subcellular

Membrane

Cell and elements

Tissue and substructures

Cell membrane

Extracellular Cell

Organ and components

Kidney

Liver

Skin